

Effects of Body Mass Index (BMI) on Pregnancy - A Prospective Observational Study on Obstetric and Fetal OutcomeManasvi Chennakeshava¹, Veena Vijayan², Rajani Somanathan³, Annamma Babu⁴, Thomas P Aliyattukudy⁵¹Assistant Professor Department of OBG, Siddaganga Medical College Research Institute, Tumakuru²Junior Consultant, OBG, Taluk Head Quarters Hospital, Thripunithura³Assistant Professor, Department of OBG, Siddaganga Medical College Research Institute⁴Senior Consultant, OBG, Medical Trust Hospital, Ernakulam⁵Senior Consultant, Reproductive Medicine, Lisie Hospital

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Abstract:**Aim and Background:** Maternal body mass index (BMI) plays a vital role in the well-being of mother and foetus. This study aims at comparing the maternal and fetal outcomes among pregnant women with low BMI, normal BMI and high BMI in local population.**Methods:** A prospective observational study conducted in a tertiary hospital from May 2022 to April 2024. (24 months)**Results:** It was noted that BMI of varied categories had significant outcome in mothers and foetus. High BMI mothers had higher risk of GDM (overweight 1.98 and obese 3.92), gestational hypertension (overweight - 2.74, obese 9.05 and morbid obese 7.06) with significant p value <0.05. Odd's ratio for preterm delivery for underweight, overweight, obese and morbid obese mothers were found to be 3.02, 1.46, 3.95, and 4.45 respectively, with significant p value <0.05. Risk for miscarriage was higher in higher BMI group of individuals with p value <0.05 and odds ratio in overweight 3.03, obese 1.95 and morbidly obese groups 8.70. Shoulder dystocia was associated with morbid obesity. The risk of PPH was also studied in this study, with increased risk in extremes of BMI (underweight 3.71, obese 3.96 and morbid obesity 15.93). Risk of hypoglycaemia and TTN was also measured and revealed risk was higher in underweight mothers and obese mothers.**Conclusion:** A conclusion was made that both low BMI and high BMI had an increased risk of pregnancy related complications as mentioned in the study. A higher incidence of GDM, gestational hypertension, miscarriage and neonatal hypoglycaemia, shoulder dystocia along with increased risk of emergency caesarean section was seen in high BMI group. In the lower BMI group, anemia and urinary tract infections was more common.**Keywords:** obesity, shoulder dystocia, body mass index, PPH.

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Introduction

Every pregnancy culminates in a healthy baby and mother, which is the main aim of obstetrician to ensure that during the pregnancy the mother is of good health. [1] Many factors contribute in having a course of uncomplicated pregnancy which results in normal growth and development of foetus. Maternal weight before and during gestation is one of the factors along with environment and genetic predisposition which influences health.

Pregnancy and neonatal outcome are determinants in having a strong effect on fetal growth with contributing factors such as pre-pregnancy weight, body mass index and gestational weight [2,3]. Two main modifiable factors influences in maternal and infant outcomes are nutrient intake and weight gain during pregnancy.[4] Gestational hypertension, pre-

eclampsia, gestational diabetes, urinary tract infection are some of the complications in pregnant women with high BMI. Intrapartum complications include higher incidence of caesarean section, malpresentation, obstetric haemorrhage, dysfunctional labour, shoulder dystocia, thrombophlebitis, fetal macrosomia and fetal asphyxia at birth.

Low maternal BMI have maternal complications such as anaemia, pre-term delivery and PPRM and fetal complications are low APGAR score, low birth weight and increased rates for perinatal mortality. Small for gestational age along with higher chances of neonatal morbidity and mortality, failure to grow, slow cognitive development and chronic diseases in adulthood. [5] In our study, we aim at studying the fetal effects of high BMI and low BMI in pregnant

women in local population.

Materials and Methods

A prospective, observational study was carried out in a tertiary care hospital, in all pregnant mothers attending antenatal clinic who fulfilled the inclusion criteria, which were, all gravid mothers of age between 19-35 years with singleton pregnancy and mothers who recorded BMI in their first trimester. But, patients with medical complications such as diabetes mellitus, systemic hypertension, chronic kidney disease and endocrine dysfunction were a part of the exclusion criteria.

During antenatal care at 1st visit in 1st trimester, BMI [weight(kg)/height(m²)] along with detailed history to rule out medical illness was recorded. Incidence of miscarriage, gestational diabetes and hypertension, anaemia, antepartum haemorrhage such as placenta previa, placenta abruption, urinary tract infection, PPRM, pre-term delivery, instrumental deliveries, emergency caesarean section deliveries, shoulder dystocia and postpartum haemorrhage

were the maternal outcome included in the study. Fetal outcomes such as small for gestational age, large for gestational age, transient tachypnoea of newborn and hypoglycaemia were also considered.

After ethical committee clearance and defining all the above mentioned outcomes in detail, the study was carried out in 256 women between May 2022 to April 2024 (24 months).

The association of 2 qualitative variables and statistical significance were analysed by Chi square test. Continuous data are presented as range, mean (SD), and 95% confidence interval and analysed with T- test, analysis of variance (ANOVA) or the Mann –Whitney U test as appropriate.

Statistical comparisons were accomplished with Microsoft Excel and SPSS v19 software. A p-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

In this study of 256 population, subjects were categorized based on BMI. (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Distribution of BMI groups (percentage)

Majority of the patients (50%) fell in to the normal BMI category and 33% were of the underweight category. In the group, only 1 patient (0.39%) was of the morbid obesity and later the complications developed in that mother included GDM, shoulder dystocia and large for gestational age baby.

On comparison with normal BMI group, the percentage of GDM that developed among normal BMI mothers was 16.53% and among overweight group was 29.24% and 43.75% among obese group of mothers.

The frequency of gestational hypertension developed doubled, from 4.13% in normal BMI to 10.59% and 28.13% in overweight and obese categories. It was also noted there was a 3 fold increase in miscarriages among overweight group where percentage was 9.41% while it remained 3.31% in mothers with normal BMI, but it was found

to be high in overweight (9.41%) and obese (6.25%) groups. The frequency of UTI was lower in lower BMI group of mothers-17.65% when compared to the normal BMI group- 6.61%

It was studied that anemia was again more, almost a 3 fold increase of 17.65% in mothers with lower BMI when compared to mothers with normal BMI- 5.79%.

The study could not find a significant difference in frequency of placenta previa and placental abruption among different categories of BMI. Preterm delivery was more common in mothers of low BMI (17.65%) followed by overweight mothers (9.41%) and then obese (7.88%) and those that fell under normal BMI was (6.61%). There was an increase in frequency of pre-term premature rupture of membranes (PPROM) and postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) in both low BMI and obese groups where PPRM was

5.88% and 6.25% respectively. Under normal BMI, PPH had a frequency of 1.65%.

Obese category women were found to have an increase in incidence of emergency caesarean section when compared to other groups (table 2). Even though the frequency in other groups were similar, the indications for surgery differed in each

categories from fetal distress in mothers of low BMI being the most common indication.

Failure of induction, failure to progress and previous caesarean section with scar pain were more common in individuals with higher BMI along with a case of shoulder dystocia as a complication noted in the morbid obese category.

Figure 2: Distribution of Emergency LSCS

When compared to normal BMI, this study finds no discernible increase in the frequency of instrumental delivery for either low or high BMI. There was only 1 mother in the morbid obese category who had complications of shoulder dystocia (100%).

Percentage of Transient tachypnea of the newborn (TTN) at comparable rates among low (11.76%), overweight (11.76%) and obese (12.50%), this

percentage was higher than in the normal BMI category (9.92%). Neonatal hypoglycemia was more common in the overweight and obese categories, as indicated by the percentage that increased from 2.48% in the normal BMI group to 4.71% in the overweight and 6.25 percent in the obese BMI groups.

Table 1: Distribution of Antenatal Complications and BMI Groups (Odds Ratio, Confidence Interval)

Pregnancy Outcome	Maternal BMI Group (kg/m ²)									
	<18.49 (95% CI)	OR	18.50-24.99 (95% CI)	OR	25.0-29.99 (95% CI)	OR	30-39.99 (95% CI)	OR	>40.00 (95% CI)	OR
Gestational Hypertension	1.45 (0.15 - 13.21)	-	1	-	2.74 (0.88-8.51)	-	9.07 (2.78 - 29.58)	-	7.06 (0.25 - 193.92)	-
GDM	1.08 (0.28 - 4.11)	-	1	-	1.98 (1.01 - 3.89)	-	3.92 (1.68 - 9.16)	-	14.85 (0.58 - 377.6)	-
Miscarriage	0.74 (0.03 - 14.46)	-	1	-	3.03 (0.88 - 10.44)	-	1.95 (0.34 - 11.1)	-	8.70 (0.30 - 244.69)	-
Anemia	3.48 (0.80 - 15.05)	-	1	-	0.59 (0.14 - 2.37)	-	0.23 (0.13 - 4.22)	-	5.08 (0.19 - 135.89)	-
Placenta Previa	0.96 (0.04-19.53)	-	1	-	0.19 (0.01-3.88)	-	0.52 (0.02-10.34)	-	11.28 (0.38-329.01)	-
Abruption	1.36 (0.06-29.64)	-	1	-	0.70 (0.06-7.93)	-	0.73 (0.03-15.7)	-	15.93 (0.51-495.42)	-
Urinary Tract Infection	3.02 (0.71-12.75)	-	1	-	1.26 (0.44-3.63)	-	0.94 (0.18-4.66)	-	4.45 (0.16-117.77)	-
PPROM	22.09 (0.86 - 565.03)	-	1	-	4.37 (0.17 - 107.17)	-	19.91 (0.93 - 425.76)	-	81.00 (1.16 - 5609.77)	-
Preterm	3.02 (0.71-12.75)	-	1	-	1.46 (0.52-4.07)	-	3.95 (1.31-11.91)	-	4.45 (0.16-117.77)	-

OR >1 means that exposure is associated with higher odds of outcome. OR<1 means that exposure is associated with lower odds of outcome. Significant odds ratio with p-value <0.05 are highlighted.

Table 2: Distribution of Intrapartum Complications and BMI Groups

Pregnancy Outcome	≤18.49 OR (95 % CI)	18.50-24.99 OR (95% CI)	25.0-25.99 OR (95% CI)	30-39.99 OR (95% CI)	≥40.00 OR (95% CI)
EmergencyLscs	0.98(0.32-2.98)	1	0.98(0.53 – 1.80)	1.41(0.62-3.20)	0.78(0.03-19.60)
Instrumental Delivery	0.74(0.03-14.46)	1	0.34(0.03-3.17)	0.40(0.02-7.65)	8.70(0.30-244.69)
Shoulder Dystocia	2.29(0.08-58.58)	1	2.89(0.25-32.41)	1.23(0.04-31.05)	241.0(6.69-8670.68)
PPH	3.71(0.31 – 43.37)	1	0.70(0.06-7.93)	3.96(0.53-29.32)	15.93(0.51-495.42)
TTN	1.21(0.24-5.94)	1	1.21(0.49-2.94)	1.29(0.38-4.33)	2.92(0.11-75.58)
Hypoglycemia	0.96(0.04-19.53)	1	1.94(0.42-8.91)	2.62(0.41-16.40)	11.28(0.38-329.01)

Discussion

With a total subjects of 256 mothers satisfying the inclusion criteria distributed according to BMI values such as underweight (BMI <18.49) , normal (BMI 18.5-24.99), over weight (BMI 25- 29.99) ,obese (BMI 30-39.99) and morbid obese (BMI > or = 40) and they were divided under each category 17, 121, 85,32 and 1, respectively.

The antenatal complications such as GDM, gestational hypertension, miscarriage, Antepartum haemorrhage (placenta previa and placental abruption), urinary tract infections, preterm delivery and PPRM were considered (table 1). It was concluded that there was a risk of GDM significantly in mothers in the overweight and obese mothers compared to normal BMI mothers with a significant p-value <0.05 and an odds ratio 1.98 in overweight category and 3.92 in obese category. Dasgupta et al, also demonstrated high incidence for GDM among obese group with odd ratio of 5.6 RCOG guideline states that “Maternal obesity is known to be an important risk factor for gestational diabetes (GDM) with a number of large cohort studies reporting a three-fold increased risk compared to women with a healthy weight”. [7]

An important p-value of <0.005 is shown for the obese group's risk of gestational hypertension. The high BMI category had a higher risk of gestational hypertension, with odds ratios of 2.74, 9.07, and 7.06 for overweight, obese, and morbidly obese individuals, respectively. Perlow et al, showed similar results with increased risk of gestational hypertension with odds ratio of 2.38 in moderate obesity and an odds ratio of 3.00 in severe obesity. [8] In our study, there is a increased risk of preterm delivery and PPRM in both low BMI and high BMI group when compared to normal BMI group. The odds ratio (OR) for underweight, overweight, obese, and morbidly obese preterm deliveries is 3.02, 1.46, 3.95, and 4.45, respectively. In morbidly obese and

obese people, the risk of premature delivery is significantly higher (p < 0.05).

The occurrence of PPRM in underweight, overweight, obese and morbid obesity was demonstrated with an odds ratio of 22.09, 4.37, 19.91 and 81.00, respectively. There was increase in incidence of spontaneous preterm delivery in low BMI group and less among the high BMI group as shown in Handler et al. [9] Whereas, in another study by Kirkpatrick, shows the effects of obesity in pregnancy showing a high risk of premature delivery among higher BMI group of mothers. [7] Davidson et al, also demonstrated the risk of preeclampsia, to being the primary risk cause of placental insufficiency and premature birth. [10]

Compared to low and normal BMI groups, the high BMI group has a considerably higher risk of miscarriage. For the categories of overweight, obese, and severely obese people, the OR for the risk of miscarriage is 3.03, 1.95, and 8.70, respectively. Bellvar J et al. provide a similar finding.

According to their research, the chance of miscarriage rises for obese women from 38.7% to 13.3% for those with normal weights. [11] Anjana Verma and Lalit Shrimali et al, were able to show that the incidence of anaemia was higher in the underweight group (58.6%) compared to the normal or high BMI group. [12] This study similarly yielded a similar outcome, with an OR of 3.48. In morbidly obese people, we also saw an increase in OR for anaemia risk. In their research, Elmar Aigner et al. came to the conclusion that morbid obesity is associated with a higher incidence of iron deficiency anaemia, which is linked to heightened blood hepcidin concentration. [13]

In their study, Usha Kiran T S et al. demonstrated that pregnant women with a BMI of greater than 30 had a higher risk of urinary tract infections. [14] Unlike a study by Sebire NJ et al., where they were

unable to show a significant risk relationship between low BMI and urinary tract infection, we were able to find an increased OR for infection for both underweight (OR 3.02) and morbid obesity (4.45) in our study. [15]

Comparing low and high BMI groups to the normal BMI group, there is no increase in the incidence of APH (placenta previa and placental abruption). Morbid obesity is associated with a higher risk of placenta previa and placenta abruption (ORs of 11.28 and 15.93, respectively). Additionally, an elevated odds ratio of 1.36 was discovered for abruptio placenta in the underweight group. Similar rates of antepartum haemorrhage were discovered by Anjana Verma and Lalit Shrimali across all 29 BMI groups. [12] Shoulder dystocia, emergency caesarean section, instrumental delivery and PPH were the other risk factors included in intrapartum complications.

According to our research, morbid obesity is linked to a higher likelihood of shoulder dystocia. In the group of people with morbid obesity, there was just one pregnant woman, and her delivery was hindered by shoulder dystocia. Angela Dinatale et al.'s study, which indicated a greater risk for shoulder dystocia in obese mothers, produced encouraging results. [16]

According to research by FC Denison et al., women who were overweight, obese, or severely obese had higher odds of needing an emergency caesarean section compared to those who were normal weight (OR 1.94, 3.40, and 14.34, respectively). [17]

"The risk of Caesareans rose gradually even in women without any other complications: OR 1.4, 95% CI 1.0–1.8 (BMI of 25–29.9), OR 1.5, 95% CI 1.1–2.1 (BMI of 30–34.9), and OR 3.1, 95% CI 2.3–4.8 (BMI 47. ≥35)," according to Dietz P M et al. [18]

In our study, the rate of emergency caesarean sections has an elevated OR of 1.41 in the obese category. The frequency of emergency caesarean sections among populations with low, normal, and overweight BMIs is nearly identical. However, there are differences in the indications for every category. Indicators of previous caesarean section with scar discomfort, failure to progress, and unsuccessful induction were more prevalent in the high BMI group. Foetal discomfort emerged as the most common indicator in the low BMI category. Shoulder dystocia hindered the vaginal delivery of the morbidly obese mother. Consequently, the rate of caesarean sections in this group could not be investigated. Morbidly obese moms have a higher OR of 8.70 for the likelihood of instrumental delivery, while FC Denison et al. found that the adjusted odds of being overweight to obese and severely obese decreased in a dose-dependent manner. [17]

Underweight, obese, and morbidly obese groups exhibit increased risk of postpartum haemorrhage (PPH) with ORs of 3.71, 3.96, and 15.93, respectively, in contrast to the normal weight group. According to Sohinee Bhattacharya et al., there is decreased risk in low BMI category, with ORs for PPH in underweight, overweight, obese, and morbidly obese being 0.8, 1.1, 1.5, and 1.3, 19 NJ Sebire et al also demonstrates decreased risk for PPH in low BMI group. [15] Transient tachypnoea of newborn, hypoglycaemia, term infants born for small for gestational age and large for gestational age are part of the fetal outcomes that was studied.

There is an increased risk of TTN for both low and high BMI when compared to normal BMI (odds ratio: underweight – 1.21, overweight – 1.21, obese – 1.29, morbidly obese – 2.92). Compared to the normal weight group, the risk of hypoglycemia in infants was high in the overweight (OR 1.94), obese (OR 2.62), and morbidly obese (OR 11.28) categories.

Among the low BMI category, there is unquestionably a high incidence of term small for gestational age infants. The percentage of SGA in the normal BMI group is 11.5%, whereas in the low BMI group, it rises to 17.6%. As we move from overweight to obese to morbidly obese, the incidence of large for gestational age infants tends to increase, with percentages of 9.4%, 28%, and 100%, respectively. In their study, Anjana Verma and Lalit Shrimali also found a similar tendency with reference to SGA and LGA newborns. [12]

A study by Meenakshi T. Sahu, Anjoo Agarwal, Vinita Das, and Amita Pandey revealed that obese mothers had a considerable risk for macrosomia, while low birth weight was significantly more common in underweight women. [20]

Conclusion

It was noted that both low and high BMI groups affected the intrapartum, antenatal and fetal complications and our study even though included a small population brings out significant results. The risk of difficulties associated to pregnancy has increased for both low and high BMI. GDM, gestational hypertension were more common among higher BMI group. Preterm birth, PPROM, PPH, and temporary tachypnea in newborn are among the pregnancy issues that are more likely to occur in women with low or high BMIs than in women with normal BMIs.

Morbid obesity has a substantial correlation with shoulder dystocia. Obesity is associated with a higher incidence of emergency caesarean sections. Low birth weight babies are more likely to belong in the low BMI group.

The incidence of large for gestational age infants is on the rise in the categories of morbidly obese, overweight, and obese people.

References

1. Park K, Park's textbook of preventive and social medicine. 22nd ed. Jabalpur: M/s Banarasidas Bhanot publishers; 2013. P.480.
2. Institute of Medicine. Subcommittee on nutritional status and weight gain during pregnancy: Nutrition during pregnancy.
3. WHO C. Maternal anthropometry and pregnancy outcomes. Geneva, WHO. 1995:1-98.
4. Institute of Medicine (US). Subcommittee on Nutritional Status, Weight Gain during Pregnancy, Institute of Medicine (US). Subcommittee on Dietary Intake, Nutrient Supplements during Pregnancy. Nutrition during pregnancy: part I, weight gain; part II, nutrient supplements. Natl Academy Pr; 1990 Jun 15
5. Barker DJ, Godfrey KM, Gluckman PD, Harding JE, Owens JA, Robinson JS. Fetal nutrition and cardiovascular disease in adult life. *The Lancet*. 1993 Apr 10; 341(8850):938-41.
6. Dasgupta A, Harichandrakumar KT, Habeebullah S. Pregnancy outcome among obese Indians - a prospective cohort study in a tertiary Care Centre in South India. *International Journal of Scientific Study*. 2014; 2(2):13-8.
7. Modder JF, Fitzsimons KJ. CMACE/RCOG joint guideline: management of women with obesity in pregnancy. Centre for Maternal and Child Enquiries and the Royal College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists; 2010.
8. Perlow JH, Morgan MA. Massive maternal obesity and perioperative cesarean morbidity. *American Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology*. 1994 Feb 1;170(2):560-
9. Usha Kiran TS, Hemmadi S, Bethel J, Evans J. Outcome of pregnancy in a woman with an increased body mass index. *BJOG: an international journal of obstetrics & gynaecology*. 2005 Jun 1; 112(6):768-72.
10. American Diabetes Association. Diagnosis and classification of diabetes mellitus. *Diabetes care*. 2010 Jan; 33(Suppl 1):S62.
11. Perlow JH, Morgan MA. Massive maternal obesity and perioperative cesarean morbidity. *American Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology*. 1994 Feb 1;170(2):560-
12. Verma A, Shrimali L. Maternal body mass index and pregnancy outcome. *Journal of clinical and diagnostic research: JCDR*. 2012 Nov; 6(9):1531.
13. Aigner E, Feldman A, Datz C. Obesity as an emerging risk factor for iron deficiency. *Nutrients*. 2014 Sep 11; 6(9):3587-600.
14. Usha Kiran TS, Hemmadi S, Bethel J, Evans J. Outcome of pregnancy in a woman with an increased body mass index. *BJOG: an international journal of obstetrics & gynaecology*. 2005 Jun 1; 112(6):768-72.
15. Sebire NJ, Jolly M, Harris JP, Wadsworth J, Joffe M, Beard RW, Regan L, Robinson S. Maternal obesity and pregnancy outcome: a study of 287 213 pregnancies in London. *International journal of obesity*. 2001 Aug; 25(8):1175.
16. Dinatale A, Ermito S, Fonti I, Giordano R, Cacciatore A, Romano M, La Rosa B. Obesity and fetal-maternal outcomes. *Journal of prenatal medicine*. 2010 Jan; 4(1):5.
17. Denison FC, Norwood P, Bhattacharya S, Duffy A, Mahmood T, Morris C, Raja EA, Norman JE, Lee AJ, and Scotland G. Association between maternal body mass index during pregnancy, short-term morbidity, and increased health service costs: a population-based study. *BJOG: An International Journal of Obstetrics & Gynaecology*. 2014 Jan 1; 121(1):72-82.
18. Dietz PM, Callaghan WM, Morrow B, Cogswell ME. Population-based assessment of the risk of primary cesarean delivery due to excess prepregnancy weight among nulliparous women delivering term infants. *Maternal and child health journal*. 2005 Sep 1;9(3):237-44
19. Bhattacharya S, Campbell DM, Liston WA, Bhattacharya S. Effect of body mass index on pregnancy outcomes in nulliparous women delivering singleton babies. *BMC public Health*. 2007 Dec;7(1):168
20. Sahu MT, Agarwal A, Das V, Pandey A. Impact of maternal body mass index on obstetric outcome. *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology Research*. 2007 Oct 1; 33(5):655-9.